

Transformation of Transformer Models: from Neurons to Visual Transformers

Soumya B S*1, Sudha L K 2,

*¹Assitant Professor, Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Dr. Ambedkar Institute of Technology, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

²Associate Professor Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering, Bangalore Institute of Technology, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Machine learning, a branch of deep learning has demonstrated phenomenal performance across various fields, including natural language processing, computer vision, , and robotics. The foundation of deep learning is built upon artificial neural networks (ANNs) that consist of numerous layers, hence the term "deep." These multilayered networks are designed to extract complex patterns from data, enabling them to effectively address complex tasks. While Computer vision techniques aim to represent the human visual system using computational models, Transfer learning utilizes insights from pre-trained models to offer an efficient and cost-effective approach for addressing various challenges in deep learning. Transfer Learning makes use of attention mechanism to capture long range dependencies. To understand advanced architectures like Visual Transformers, it is essential to grasp the fundamental building blocks. This study aims to assess and contrast various Transformer models under different configurations and mathematical analyses. It seeks to identify the crucial elements that could enhance transformer performance and propose upcoming research areas for further advancement in this field.

Keywords: Deep Learning, CNN, Neural networks, Transformer Model, Attention Mechanism, Vision Transformer (ViT)

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence [AI] refers to the theory and development of computers and machines that can reason, learn, and behave in ways that normally require human intelligence, such as visual perception, decision making, speech recognition and translation. Machine learning is a branch of AI that allows systems to automatically learn and adapt from experience, without human programming. Deep neural networks have been successfully used in diverse emerging domains to solve real-world complex problems with many deep learning (DL) architectures.

In the field of sequence modeling and transduction tasks, such as language modeling and machine translation, recurrent neural networks, particularly long short-term memory and gated recurrent neural networks, have established themselves as the leading approaches. While recent advancements have significantly enhanced computational efficiency, the fundamental limitation of sequential computation persists. Attention mechanisms have emerged as a crucial component in powerful sequence modeling and transduction models across various tasks, enabling the modeling of dependencies regardless of their distance in input or output sequences [1]. Transformer, in which the attention mechanism is a core component of its architecture, is a eminent deep learning model that has been widely adopted in different fields, such as natural language processing (NLP), speech processing, and computer vision (CV) [2]. This paper proposes the essential aspects of the transformer model covering foundational works and subsequent advancements in applying transformer architectures to vision tasks from basic building blocks from neurons, perceptrons, CNN, RNN, and transformer self-attention mechanisms to vision transformers.

I. It covers the traditional aspects of different deep learning architectures and transformer models, from the basic encoder-decoder model to the vision transformer.

II. Identify essential aspects that can further improve Transformers and also suggest promising research directions for future development

II. FUNDAMENTAL WORK

A. Neuron

Neuron is a simple binary switch and act as a basic logic gate. The basic unit of a neural network is a neuron (or a node). The input to the neuron is Boolean, and the threshold (θ) is the hardcore. The neuron either fires or does not fire, based on whether the threshold is exceeded.

Fig 1. Neuron structure

$$y = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \sum_{i=0}^n x_i \geq \theta \\ 0 & \text{if } \sum_{i=0}^n x_i < \theta \end{cases}$$

B. Perceptron

A perceptron [3] is a type of simulated neuron structure in a neural network that includes one or more inputs, performs a weighted sum of these inputs, adds a bias, and then applies an activation function. The input to the perceptron is real input, the output is binary, and it can deal with linearly separable functions. The activation function [4] can be either linear or nonlinear depending on the function it represents and is used to control the outputs of our neural networks across different domains from object recognition and classification. The weighted sum is given as

$$\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b$$

for each input x_i multiplied by the weight w_i with the bias term b added and the result is passed through an activation function f .

$$f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b\right)$$

Activation Functions in Deep Learning Models introduce non-linearity, making it capable of learning complex patterns,[4] allows neurons to learn complex features from input data, determine whether the neuron ‘fires’ or not, influencing the network's decision making capability. Some activation functions (e.g., ReLU and its variants) help mitigate vanishing and exploding gradient problems, which can hamper training in deep networks. A perceptron is an extension of a neuron [3]. Single layer perceptron, as shown in Figure 2, can simulate logic and, logic or, logic not, and logic and not operations, but it can't realize logic XOR

Fig 2: The structure of Single-layer Perceptron

Algorithm 1 Perceptron Learning Algorithm

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P : inputs with label 1;
N: inputs with label 0;
Initialize w=[w0, w1, w2,.. . wn] randomly;
while !convergence do
pic random x ∈ P U N ;
    if x ∈ P and if  $\sum_{i=0}^n w_i * x_i < 0$  then
        w=w+x ;
    end
    if x ∈ P and if  $\sum_{i=0}^n w_i * x_i \geq 0$  then
        w=w-x ;
    end
end
end
    
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The algorithm converges if all inputs are classified correctly, with no further corrections. Perceptron cannot handle XOR and !XOR functions. XOR requires a nonlinear decision boundary that cannot be implemented using a single layer perceptron.

C. Multi-Layer Perceptron

To simulate XOR, a multilayer perceptron (MLP) with at least two layers, one hidden layer, and one output layer, is required. The hidden layer can learn to represent the nonlinear relationship between the inputs, thereby allowing the output layer to learn the XOR operation. Neurons are organized into layers. The input layer receives [1] the initial data for training the neural network, which comes in various formats from images, videos, texts, speech, sounds, or numeric data. The number of neurons corresponds to the number of features in the input. Hidden Layers are made up of mostly convolutional and pooling layers, of which the convolutional layers detect the local patterns and features in data from the previous (layer, which are the intermediate layers that perform computations and feature extraction). Deep-learning models have multiple hidden layers. The output Layer produces the final prediction. The number of neurons and the activation function depend on the task (e.g., classification, regression)

Fig 3: block diagram of deep learning model
 Number of input neurons = features; Number of output neurons = classes

D. Training the model

The training process [2] begins by defining the model and then invoking the fit-generator method. The dataset is divided into batches. A batch is a set or group of data elements. Batch size denotes the total number of training elements in a particular batch. Essentially [2] the model then compares the generated output with the actual output, and the difference is calculated. In order to reduce the difference, the generated output is backpropagated into the model. The model adjusts the weights and repeats the same process until it converges. This leads to the search for an algorithm that accelerates the learning process and generates an optimal output. In this direction several optimization algorithms [3] have been developed and implemented on various tasks.

Fig 4: Various optimization algorithms on datasets

The testing stage presents better results for all the datasets with Adam algorithm. Optimization algorithms with varying parameters like learning rate, number of filters, and so on for future study

E. Regularization techniques

These techniques [3] are used to prevent overfitting (where the model learns the training data too well and performs poorly on unseen data) and to improve the generalization performance of deep neural networks. Some of the most commonly used regularization techniques include L1 and L2 regularization, dropout, and early termination. A classical neural network is a multilayer perceptron (MLP) with multiple linear layers of fully connected neurons and nonlinear activation functions. In computer vision, convolutional neural networks

incorporate convolutional layers to process images, whereas recurrent neural networks(RNN) employ recurrent cells to process sequential data, particularly in Natural Language Processing (NLP), which exhibits short-term dependencies associated with exploding and vanishing gradients. Additionally, RNNs are hampered by their slow training speed owing to their sequential data processing and computational approach. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, a variant of recurrent networks, overcome these limitations while also alleviating gradient descent issues and expanding the memory capacity for NLP tasks. However, LSTM sequential processing remains a challenge that hinders the extraction of contextual meanings.

III. Deep Neural Networks:

A. Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs)

Fig 5: A simple CNN architecture [4]

A simplified CNN architecture for MNIST classification as shown in Figure 5. CNN-based models [5] have attempted to capture long-range dependencies by adding a self-attention layer at either the spatial or channel level. Recently, convolution layers with self-attention layers have been replaced by augmented CNNs, resulting in improved object detection and image classification tasks. Interestingly even by combining attention and convolution features convincing results are obtained with same computation and size of the model restrictions, self-attention only architecture also have replaced image classification significantly.

B. Basic Transformer Model

The basic Transformer model[6], as introduced in the original paper "Attention is All You Need," is applied to sequence-to-sequence autoregression.

i) Attention Mechanism:

This new simple network architecture uses multihead attention mechanisms and point-wise feed-forward networks, based solely on attention mechanisms, dispensing with recurrence, and convolutions entirely. The Transformer consists of both an encoder and a decoder.

Fig 5: The transformer model architecture [6]

With query, keys, and values and the output are all vectors, a set of key-value pairs are mapped to an output by an attention function. compatibility function of the query with the corresponding key computes the weights off values and his weighted sum of values in turn compute the output.

Dot product of the query and keys is divided by $\sqrt{d_k}$ then a softmax function is applied to get the weights and values. Then on a set of queries self-attention is computed simultaneously and packed together into matrix Q. Matrices K and V are packed with keys and values respectively[6][7][8]. The output matrix is computed as

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{Sroftmax} \left(\frac{Q K^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V$$

Fig 6: scaled Dot-Product attention Multi-Head attention

Multi-head attention allows the model to jointly attend to information from different representation subspaces at different positions[9].

$$\text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V) = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h) W^o$$

$$\text{Where head}_i = \text{Attention}(QW_i^Q, KW_i^K, VW_i^V)$$

The total computational cost is similar to that of single-head attention with full dimensionality because each head has reduced dimension. Research suggests that attention mechanisms can perform convolution-like operations, despite the fact that optimal results are achieved when attention and convolutional features are combined. Notably, under equivalent computational and model size limitations, architectures relying solely on self-attention can achieve comparable accuracy in image classification tasks[10].

C. Model Usage:

The Transformer architecture [11] can typically be used in three distinct manners:

- Encoder-Decoder. Represents full Transformer architecture. This method is typically used in sequence-to-sequence modelling (e.g., neural machine translation).
- Encoder only. Utilizing only the encoder component, the system employed the encoder's output as a representation of the input sequence. This approach is commonly applied in tasks involving classification or sequence labeling.
- Decoder only. Only the decoder is used by removing encoder-decoder cross-attention module. This is generally used in language modelling.

ii) Self-attention Analysis

The benefits of self-attention with three typically used layers can be summarised (as shown in Table1) by comparing maximum path length, sequential operations and the complexity per layer.

Layer Type	Complexity per layer	Sequential operations	Maximum path length
self-attention	$\mathcal{O}(T^2 \cdot D)$	$\mathcal{O}(1)$	$\mathcal{O}(1)$
Fully Connected	$\mathcal{O}(T^2 \cdot D^2)$	$\mathcal{O}(1)$	$\mathcal{O}(1)$
Convolutional	$\mathcal{O}(K \cdot T \cdot D^2)$	$\mathcal{O}(1)$	$\mathcal{O}(\text{Log}_K(T))$
Recurrent	$\mathcal{O}(T \cdot D^2)$	$\mathcal{O}(T)$	$\mathcal{O}(T)$

Table1: complexity at different layers where T is the length of sequence and D represents dimension of the model
 1. Self-attention and fully connected layers have the same path length, making it suitable for long-range dependencies. In Comparison with fully connected layers, self-attention layer is more parameter-efficient along with being flexible in handling variable-length inputs.

2. Since convolution layers have limited receptive field, a deep network is typically stacked to have a global receptive field. The maximum path length being constant in self-attention enables efficient modeling of long-range dependencies, requiring only a constant number of layers.

3. The self-attention layers are more parallelizable and better at long-range modelling than recurrent layers [10] due to constant sequential operations and maximum path length.

D. From Language to Vision -Vision Transformers

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and self-attention mechanisms have inspired visual transformers[5]. Images with the self-attention required each pixel attend to every other pixel. for Transformers that accept

sequential inputs ViT split input image into a series of non-overlapping patches which are projected into patch embeddings. On the patch embedding a 1D learnable position encoding is added to retain the spatial information and the encoder is fed with the joint embeddings as shown in fig7. Then to aggregate the Global representation, learnt token is attached with patch embedding and this serves as the final output for classification. For image classification task the model is trained in supervised fashion [12].

ViT structures mentioned in (Lorenzo Papa,2024) [13] into four categories by adopting the following reported methodology:

- Compact architecture (CA)[13]- Approaches designed to minimize the expense of self-attention are examined to ensure the Vision Transformer's comprehensive grasp of input features, thus decreasing the computational demands of these architectures.
- Pruning(P)-seeks to develop methods for reducing the quantity of neurons and connections in ViT models, thus preserving high accuracy while addressing issues of overparameterization and excessive computational operations (multiplications).
- Knowledge distillation (KD)-learning technique designed to improve the performance of shallow (student) models and sharing and compressing the knowledge of deeper ones (teacher) are analysed.
- Quantization (Q)- To achieve lightweight and memory efficient models, quantization techniques aims to reduce data type from floating point to integer and Precision from 32 bit to lower bit-rate of ViT's weights and activation functions.

Fig 7: Illustration of ViT [11]

The architecture of the model was nearly identical to that of the first transformer proposed in 2017 “Attention Is All You Need.”, with only minor changes allowing it to analyse images instead of words.[12]

i) *Back ground on vision transformers:*

A sequence of embedded data is extracted from the input RGB image. Next, each embedded sequence is processed by a transformer encoder, consisting of multiple self-attention layers, to capture low-level features and complex relationships within the input sequences. Lastly, an MLP head with two feed-forward layers, utilized to calculate the output probabilities. The input $x \in R^{H \times W \times C}$ image is first split into N patches. Each patch is then flattened into a sequence of n elements and projected onto a d-dimensional space using a trainable embedding tensor, which learns a linear transformation for each patch; this results in embedded patches of shape $l \times d$, generally denoted as $N \in R^{n \times d}$. Subsequently, a trainable positional embedding is then added to the sequence of projected patches allowing the model to represent spatial information of each patch within the image space[12].

ii) *Mathematical formulation of the self-attention mechanism*[12]

The operation begins by computing three matrices - Q query, K key, and V value - from the input vector, where each matrix has the same size ($d_q = d_k = d_v$). The operation then applies the softmax function to the computed scores, yielding a probability distribution

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{Q K^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V$$

The time and memory requirements for this operation scale quadratically with the number of patches (n) in an image, resulting in a computational complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. The computational cost stems from two dot product operations: the calculation of $\frac{Q K^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}$, requiring $\mathcal{O}(n^2 d_k)$ operations, and the subsequent dot product between the

softmax probabilities and V , necessitating $\mathcal{O}(n^2d_v)$ operations. The self-attention modules are concatenated to form a Multi-Head Self-Attention (MSA) module, enabling the simultaneous extraction of information from different areas. The normalized inputs and outputs of the MSA module are then processed by a feedforward network (FNN) comprising two feed-forward layers, with a nonlinear GeLU activation function applied between the layers. Let X denote the input features to the transformer module. The output of the module, X_{out} , can be formulated as follows[12]:

$$X_{MSA} = Norm (MSA (X, X)) + X$$

$$X_{out} = Norm (FNN (X_{MSA})) + X_{MSA}$$

Cross-attention: The approach described in [13] employs two distinct embedding sequences. It calculates the matrix Q from one sequence and derives K and V from the other. This method necessitates performing the patch embedding operation twice for each embedded data set. By doing so, it equips deep learning models with supplementary information, such as textual cues or additional images.

Accuracy: The Transformer, especially in its ViT incarnation, achieves high accuracy on ImageNet-1K, particularly when pre-trained on large datasets like JFT-300M, showing the power of self-attention mechanisms in capturing long-range dependencies in images. **Computational Cost:** While ViT models can outperform CNNs in terms of accuracy, they require significantly more computation due to the quadratic complexity of attention with respect to token (patch) count. This leads to higher inference times and FLOPs.

Scalability: Transformer models scale well with increased data and model size, often showing performance improvements, but this scalability comes with increased computational demands.

Efficiency: Techniques like token pruning, sparse attention, or distillation can be employed to reduce computational cost without significantly sacrificing performance.

iii) *Evaluation Metrics and Mathematical Definitions*

1. Top-1 Accuracy:

$$Top-1 Accuracy = \frac{Number\ of\ correct\ Top - 1\ predictions}{Total\ number\ of\ predictions}$$

2. Top-5 Accuracy:

$$Top-5 Accuracy = \frac{Number\ of\ samples\ where\ true\ label\ is\ in\ Top\ 5\ predictions}{Total\ number\ of\ samples}$$

It measures if the ground truth is within the model's top five predictions, useful for scenarios where multiple correct labels could exist.

3. Inference Time: Measured in milliseconds (ms) per image, indicating the computational latency during inference.
4. FLOPs (Floating Point Operations):

$$FLOPs = \sum layers (Number\ of\ Operations\ per\ Layer)$$

Quantifies the computational complexity, typically in gigaflops (GFLOPs).

5. Parameter Count:

$$Parameters = \sum_{weights} (Size\ of\ Weight\ Matrix)$$

Counts the trainable parameters, influencing model size, training time, and memory usage.

IV. OBSERVATIONS

Feature/Attribute	Basic Transformer Model	Vision Transformer Model (ViT)
Model Type	Sequence-to-sequence autoregression	Visual recognition
Key Mechanism	Multi-head attention	Attention mechanisms
Application	Sequence transduction	Object detection & image analysis
ImageNet-1k Performance	Not applicable	Achieved state-of-the-art (SoTA) performance on ImageNet-1k with largescale pre-training (specific performance varies)

Table 2: Comparison of vision tasks using Transformer and ViT models

Accuracy: The Transformer, especially in its ViT incarnation, achieves high accuracy on ImageNet-1K, particularly when pre-trained on large datasets, showing the power of self-attention mechanisms in capturing long-range dependencies in images.

Computational Cost: While ViT models can outperform CNNs in terms of accuracy, they require significantly more computation due to the quadratic complexity of attention with respect to token (patch) count. This leads to higher inference times and FLOPs.

Scalability: Transformer models scale well with increased data and model size, often showing improvements in performance, but this scalability comes with increased computational demands.

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Metric	Transformer (ViT)	Observations
Top-1 Accuracy	~83-86%	High accuracy, competitive with or surpassing many CNNs when trained on large data.
Top-5 Accuracy	~96-98%	Excellent, reflecting the model's ability to capture multiple correct predictions.
Inference Time	~100-200ms/image	Higher than traditional CNNs due to the computational cost of self-attention on large image patches
FLOPs	~55-100 GFLOPS (model dependent)	High computational overhead, especially with models like ViT-L/16, but can be optimized.
Parameter Count	~86M(ViT-Base) to ~307M(ViT-Large)	Large model size, which can be a drawback for deployment on resource-constrained devices.

Table 3: summary of ViT performance

Transformers applied to vision tasks, particularly ViT, have shown competitive performance on ImageNet-1K. ImageNet is an image classification benchmark which contains 1.28M training images and 50K validation images of 1000 classes

Limitation of the study

The trained model performance depends on the training dataset to a great extent. Fine tuning of the model is an absolute necessity, as the IoT networks/devices tend to change dynamically.

V. CONCLUSION

The Transformer model exhibits faster training times for translation tasks compared to architectures utilizing recurrent or convolutional layers. Additionally, it shows improved performance over conventional models based on recurrence. Vision Transformer (ViT) has demonstrated comparable or even better performance than leading Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) approaches across various image recognition benchmarks. Nevertheless, when faced with limited training data, ViT's ability to generalize effectively tends to diminish. Excellent results can be attained using Visual Transformers (ViT) when compared to state of art CNNs while requiring substantially fewer computational resources to train. Unlike Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Transformers do not possess certain inductive biases[11] such as translation equivariance, stationary statistics and locality. As a result, they struggle to generalize effectively when the training data is limited in quantity. The scientific community[13] has widely embraced Transformers, as evidenced by their high citation rates, indicating their significant influence in the field. Models that have also contributed to break throughs in the advancement of transformer applications complexity arise in Transformers when trying to optimise due to their large scale and substantial resource demands. The importance of model compression [12] becomes Paramount especially when trying to leverage the benefits of these large models on small edge devices. several recent papers indicate that compression methods like pruning and quantization are notably more effective for Vision Transformers (ViTs) compared to Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). With Transformers playing an ever-growing role in diverse applications, efficient optimization strategies are becoming increasingly crucial.

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